

**Chemical Examination of *Cuscuta Reflexa*, Roxb.
Part IV. Isolation of a New Yellow Flavone
Colouring Matter from the Seeds.**

BY RADHA RAMAN AGARWAL.

In previous communications from these laboratories the chemical examination of the stems of *Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb (Syn. Amarbel) has been fully described by Agarwal and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 384, 586). In the present investigation the seeds of this drug have been put to a thorough examination.

Dymock ("Pharmacographica Indica", Vol II, p. 548) separated a bitter and glucosidal resin from the seeds in addition to quercitrin. An alkaloidal principle was also present in traces which failed to give any special colour reactions. As a result of our investigations we have been able to isolate a fixed oil (3%), cuscutalin (0.05%), a flavone colouring matter called by the author as amarbelin (0.1%), amorphous bitter resin (1.0%) and reducing sugars. The oil has already been worked up separately (Agarwal and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 264). Amarbelin has the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{16}O_7, H_2O$ and preliminary examination readily reveals its nature as a colouring matter belonging to the flavone group. It gives a deep green colour with ferric chloride and forms a diacetyl and dibenzoyl derivative. The determination of the methoxyl groups in the usual manner establishes the presence of three methoxyl groups in the molecule. This proves that it is a dihydroxytrimethoxyflavone. Caustic potash fusion of amarbelin gives protocatechuic acid and a phenol which could not be identified due to lack of sufficient material but it does not give tests for phloroglucinol. Amarbelin is stable to atmospheric oxidation in alkaline solution which points to a methoxyl group being in position 3. The remaining two methoxyl groups seem to be present in the fused benzene ring. The following constitution is suggested at present for amarbelin.

Demethylation of amarbelin in the usual manner gives a product which could not be obtained in a state of sufficient purity for analysis, but its alkaline solution is not stable to aerial oxidation proving thereby the presence of a flavonol derivative. It is not identical either to quercitin or morin, and has been named amarbelitin.

Pharmacologically amarbelin is supposed to give interesting results in view of the fact that calycopterin, isolated by Ratnagiriswaran and others (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, **28**, 1964) from the leaves of *Calycopteris floribunda*, which was shown to be a dihydroxytetramethoxy-flavone was found to have anthelmintic properties. Since the seeds are also reputed to be anthelmintic a thorough and detailed study of its physiological properties will be undertaken at the King George's Medical College, Lucknow.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An authentic sample of the seeds of *Cuscuta reflexa* was obtained from the Punjab, dried in shade and was crushed to a fine powder. When burnt completely it left 10.28% of a dirty white ash consisting of 25.05% of water-soluble and 74.95% of water-insoluble inorganic material. The following radicals and elements were detected in the ash: sodium (traces), potassium, calcium, magnesium, carbonates, phosphates, chlorides and nitrates.

Sample of finely crushed material was then extracted in a Soxhlet's apparatus successively when the following amounts of extracts dried at 100° were obtained.

Benzene extract (3%).—A green coloured oil was obtained.

Chloroform extract (4%).—A yellowish green coloured mass giving colour with ferric chloride and a yellow precipitate with lead acetate was obtained. It reduces Fehling's solution.

Ethyl acetate extract (5.9%).—A yellow amorphous mass, which gives a deep green colour with ferric chloride and a deep yellow precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate. It reduces Fehling's solution and ammoniacal silver nitrate. With alkalis a beautiful yellow colour is developed.

Acetone extract (2.8%).—A yellow amorphous mass having properties similar to above.

Alcoholic extract (9.6%).—A greyish yellow amorphous mass. The powdered material (3.5 kg.) was repeatedly extracted with benzene and the dark green coloured oil obtained (105 g.) was worked up separately (*cf.* Agarwal and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) The defatted mass of the seeds was then dried completely from benzene and extracted several times with ethyl alcohol (96%). The combined alcoholic extracts were then concentrated till the major portion of the solvent was removed, whereby a greenish orange yellow syrupy mass was obtained (300 g.) It was then thoroughly refluxed with benzene in order to remove oil and chlorophyll and dissolved in alcohol. The alcoholic solution was treated with an excess of alcoholic lead acetate to remove tannins. The lead salt was decomposed in the usual manner but nothing crystalline or chemically definite product could be isolated.

The tannin-free original alcoholic extract was then evaporated to dryness and the residue dissolved in hot water. The aqueous solution was next treated with a solution of basic lead acetate and the yellow precipitate obtained was collected, washed thoroughly with water and decomposed by sulphuretted hydrogen in alcoholic suspension. The yellow alcoholic solution after removal of lead sulphide was then freed from hydrogen sulphide by passing a current of air, and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The reddish yellow brittle amorphous mass was washed repeatedly with ether and carbon disulphide and crystallised several times from hot water as soft lemon yellow tufts, m. p. 234°, yield 3.45 g. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in clusters of needles.

It has been named *amarbelin* after the Indian name of the plant from which it has been obtained. It is easily soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohols, acetone, ethyl acetate, glacial acetic acid, pyridine, less so in chloroform, benzene, nitrobenzene, amyl alcohol and water and insoluble in carbon disulphide, petroleum ether, ligroin, toluene and ether. It dissolves in sodium carbonate solution and in caustic alkalis with a bright yellow colour and is reprecipitated on acidification. The alkaline solution is sufficiently stable to aerial oxidation. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid (bright yellow colour which changes to orange yellow on warming), concentrated nitric acid (red) and in concentrated hydrochloric acid (pale yellow). With alcoholic ferric chloride it gives a green colour and with alcoholic lead acetate a deep yellow precipitate, and a chocolate silver salt with silver nitrate. The yellow

solution of the substance in glacial acetic acid is turned crimson red on the addition of a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid and greenish black which gradually turns brownish on the addition of ferric chloride. It forms crystalline oxonium salts with mineral acids and with alcoholic potassium acetate yellow needles are slowly deposited on keeping. It gives no derivatives with hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine or semicarbazide, does not reduce Fehling's solution and is non-glucosidic in character. In methyl alcoholic solution the substance on treatment with metallic magnesium and hydrochloric acid gives a bright red solution showing that it is a colouring matter belonging to the flavone group. [Found (in sample dried at 120°) : C, 62.8, 62.4; H, 5.0, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 62.79; H, 4.65 per cent. Found (air dried sample): C, 59.2, 59.75; H, 5.5, 5.45; H_2O , 4.3; M.W. (lead salt) 359, 352 (ebullisopic in alcohol) 348, 352; OMe, 26.1, 25.1, 25.9. $C_{15}H_7O_4$ (OMe)₃, H_2O requires C, 59.7; H, 5.0; H_2O , 4.9; OMe, 25.6 per cent. M.W., 362].

The *Lead salt* was formed as bright yellow amorphous mass. (Found: Pb, 22.8. $C_9H_9O_{14}$ Pb requires Pb, 23.2 per cent).

The *Silver salt*, prepared from the ammonium salt and silver nitrate in the usual manner, was obtained as a chocolate powder. (Found: Ag, 23.2. $C_{18}H_{15}O_7Ag$ requires Ag, 22.9 per cent).

Diacetylamarbelin, obtained by heating for 2 hours amarbelin (0.8 g.), acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and a few drops of pyridine, crystallised from alcohol in colourless small needles, m.p. 152°. It gives no colouration with alkaline solutions. (Found: C, 61.49; H, 5.0. $C_{22}H_{20}O_9$ requires C, 61.69; H, 4.67 per cent).

Dibenzoylamarbelin, prepared from amarbelin (1 g.), pyridine (25 c.c.) and benzoyl chloride (10 c.c.) in the usual manner, solidified on keeping for about a week. It crystallised from alcohol in microscopic colourless needles, m.p. 160° (decomp.) after previous shrinking at 124°. It gives no colour with caustic soda. (Found: C, 69.22; H 4.50. $C_{32}H_{24}O_9$ requires C, 69.56; H 4.35 per cent).

Amarbelitin.—Amarbelin (0.8 g.) was heated with hydroiodic acid (d 1.79, 12 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 130-135° for about 5 hours. After leaving overnight the reddish yellow flakes of amarbelitin hydroiodide were decomposed by boiling with acetic acid and water for about half an hour. It crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as colourless flakes, shrinking at 190° and melting at 204-205° (decomp.). It is very slightly soluble in water and readily soluble in alcohol. An alcoholic solution gives an olive green colour with ferric chloride which becomes brownish

red on keeping. It gives a reddish orange precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate. It gives a beautiful yellow colour with sodium hydroxide. A sufficient quantity of amarbelitin was not obtained for analysis.

Caustic potash fusion of Amarbelin.—Amarbelin (2 g.) and caustic potash (20 g. in 5 c.c. of water) were heated together for 4 hours at 120-130° in a nickel crucible till the yellow colour was changed to brown. The melt on cooling was extracted with water and neutralised with sulphuric acid. A dirty brown amorphous product separated which was filtered, washed and crystallised from dilute alcohol as cream coloured micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 168°. The quantity obtained was too small to admit of identification.

The filtrate was then repeatedly extracted with ether, the ethereal solution extracted with saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The bicarbonate extract was neutralised with sulphuric acid and concentrated, whereby a chocolate coloured substance separated. The mother liquor was extracted with ether and ethereal extracts evaporated to dryness. The combined product was then purified through its lead salt when colourless needles were obtained, m.p. 194°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate and less so in water. It gives a reddish colouration with ferric chloride and reduces ammoniacal silver nitrate. From all its reactions and properties it is identified as protocatechuic acid. A mixed m.p. with Merck's pure protocatechuic acid is 194°.

The phenolic portion, obtained after the separation of the acid by bicarbonate, extraction of the ether and evaporation of the solvent, was dissolved in caustic soda. On working it up in the usual manner an amorphous substance was obtained from which nothing definite could be isolated. It failed to give any reaction for phloroglucinol.

The resin of the decomposed basic lead salt obtained after the separation of amarbelin by water failed to give any other product. It was of a dark greyish brown colour with a metallic lustre and melted indefinitely at 100-104°, yield 35 g.

The filtrate after the separation of the lead salt by basic lead acetate was freed from lead by passing a current of sulphuretted hydrogen and concentrated. It reduced Fehling's solution readily and contained a large amount of reducing sugars.

In conclusion the author wishes to express his deep sense of gratitude to Dr. S. Dutt, D.Sc. for his valuable help and guidance. He

is also indebted to the 'Kanta Prasad Trust' of the Allahabad University for grant of a research scholarship which enabled him to investigate this problem.

S U M M A R Y.

1. A flavone colouring matter named amarbelin has been isolated from the seeds of *Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb.

2. Amarbelin has been shown to be a dihydroxytrimethoxyflavone. Amarbelin gives protocatechuic acid on caustic potash fusion. Demethylation of amarbelin gives a product different from quercetin or morin and named as amarbelitin.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

Received March 20, 1936.

Spiro-compounds. Part I. A New Route to Spiro-compounds. Synthesis of *cyclo*Hexane-spiro-*cyclopentane*

BY NRIPENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE.

The valency deflexion hypothesis has been supported by Thorpe, Ingold and co-workers by the work on the formation and stability of spiro-compounds (*cf.* Thorpe and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080; 1919, 115, 320; 1921, 119, 1199; 1922, 121, 1496; 1926, 2011; Kon, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 810; 1922, 573; Birch, Gough and Kon, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1315; Paul, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 717).

The methods available for the preparation of such compounds are limited in number and a new general method has been described in this paper. This consists in condensing the sodium salt of the dicyano ester (I), formed by the condensation of a ketone-cyanohydrin with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate (Higson and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1455) with a monohalogenated ester to yield the product (II).